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Kakkēka rukusma (« Ceins tes armes ! »)

2^e Rencontre d'Histoire militaire du Proche-Orient ancien
(Lyon, 17-18 octobre 2013)

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Textes édités par Philippe Abrahams et Catherine Wolff

Actes du colloque international
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THE WEAPONRY OF THE MIDDLE ASSYRIAN ARMY
ACCORDING TO THE WRITTEN SOURCES*

During the Old Assyrian period (2025-1500 BC), the city of Assur was an active commercial centre, which made treaties with other cities along the trade routes. No remarkable military endeavours are attested for the city during this period.¹

This situation changed during the second half of the second mill. BC, when the Assyrian kingdom expanded territorially for the first time. The Assyrian kings of the 13th century BC, Adad-nārāri I (1295-1264 BC), Shalmaneser I (1263-1234 BC) and Tukulti-Ninurta I (1233-1197 BC) annexed the territories in the Jazirah (the former kingdom of Mittani), conquered the surrounding mountainous regions to the north and the east, and, for a brief period of time, even managed to subjugate Babylonia during the reign of Tukulti-Ninurta I.

The military campaigns of the Middle Assyrian kings were based on a strong and relative recently formed army. The organisation of the Middle Assyrian army has already been studied,² but no comprehensive discussion of the weapons used by the Assyrian warriors during this period has been carried out to date. This is probably the result of the type of sources available for the period, which, until recently, have been mainly the royal inscriptions. Documentation of this kind is rich in ethnological or territorial details. However, while they are often detailed in terms of ideological and geographical information, telling us which territories were annexed, or which kings were defeated, the description of the weapons receives very little attention. Recently, some more informative documentation regarding the study of the weaponry, from Assur and other sites (Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta, Dūr-Katlimmu and Harbe), has been published.³

The aim of this paper is to study the weapons at the disposal of a Middle Assyrian warrior as they are recorded in the written sources of the period.

In a study of this nature it is impossible to describe all the instruments that could be used as weapons. Moreover, as the archival documentation does not distinguish

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1. Dercksen 2004, p. 155-159; Veenhof, Eidem 2008, p. 122-146.

2. Jakob 2003, p. 191-222; Postgate 2008, p. 83-92.

3. The archival Middle Assyrian documentation and bibliography published until September 2013 has been taken into consideration with the exception of the recent volume by Reculeau, Feller 2012. I was not able to systematically consider Postgate 2013, which I could use after this article had already been submitted.

between weapons and everyday tools, often we only have the context to help us decide whether a particular object was used for military purpose.⁴

In classifying the weapons below, I follow the rather intuitive division established by E. Salonen who differentiates between defensive and offensive weapons.⁵

1. Defensive weapons

Obviously, one of the first defensive “weapons” was the soldier’s attire. J.N. Postgate has already discussed the main types of military dress and it is not necessary to go over it again here.⁶ The list below summarises the military uniforms discussed by J.N. Postgate (2001, p. 387):

- kusītu* “robe”
- naḥlaptu* (some kind of coat)
- elēnītu* “fringed shawl”
- sāgu* “kilt”
- šipirtu* “woven girdle”
- gulēnu* “tunic”
- šupālitu* “shirt”
- šupālitu ḥalluptu* “mail shirt”
- urnutu* (shirt or tunic)

Boots (*šuhuppātu*)⁷ are present among the evidence, but they are rarely mentioned in relation to the military.⁸ Boots were worn by some soldiers, probably the ones belonging to elite units. It is conceivable that Assyrian soldiers wore some kind of foot protection, because good footwear was necessary especially when fighting in mountainous regions. Some of the types of boots carry the name of the countries where they originated (e.g. *katmuḥāju*).⁹ These boots were made of leather¹⁰ and felt (*taḥapšu*).¹¹

4. See below under the diverse entries; e.g. *patru* in *MARV 2*, 6; *akkullu*; *kakku* can also mean “tool”, Jakob 2003, p. 108 n. 237 (on TCH 90.G.23).

5. Salonen 1965. He is followed e.g. by Waetzoldt 1990, p. 1-38.

6. Postgate 2001, p. 373-388.

7. Salonen 1969, p. 46-48; *AHw.* 1262a, without translation; *CAD Š/III*, 210 f. “boot (?)”; *CDA* 326b “boot(s)”.

8. Possibly ⁴⁾ 30-*šu* ^{KUS}Š[ÚḪUB^{MES}] ⁵⁾ *a-na* ÉRIN^{MES} *ša* É.GAL-[*lim*], “30 pairs of boots for the people of the palace”, *MARV 9*, 29: 4-5 and see also lines 21'-22'.

9. ¹⁸⁾1-*ni-a-tu* ^{KUS}šu-*ḥu-pa-tu* ¹⁹⁾*ku-tu-mu-ḥa-ia-tu*, “one pair of Katmuhean boots”, Postgate 1973, pl. 13, n°. 1: 18-19 (*CAD Š/III*, 211); ^{KUS}šu-*ḥu-pa-te* *ša ku-ut-mu-ḥa-ia-a-ta*, *MARV 3*, 64: 8 (Freydank, Saporetti 1989, p. 36, 75).

10. [^{KU}]šu-ḥu-pa-te, Weidner 1954-1956, p. 274: 43; ^{KUS}ŠÚḪUB^{MES}, Beckman, Foster 1988, p. 5 n°. 2: 11' (*CAD Š/III*, 211); ^{KUS}šu-*ḥu-pa-te*, *MARV 3*, 64: 6.8.13 (Freydank, Saporetti 1989, p. 36, 75); and attestations in n. 8-9 above.

11. ¹³⁾*ta-ḥap-šu a-na* ^{KUS}šu-*ḥu-pa-te* ¹⁴⁾*ša aš-šu-ra-ya-a-ta la-aš-šu*, “there is no felt for boots of the Assyrian (type)”, *MARV 3*, 64: 13-14 (Freydank, Saporetti 1989, p. 36, 75); Postgate 2000, p. 213.

The defensive weapons were helmets (or hats), the armour and shields.

1.1. Helmets

In his article “Helm” (helmet) for the *Reallexikon der Assyriologie*, Wilcke noted that no word for helmet was available in Sumerian or Akkadian in the third mill. BC, and that both languages used the word SAGŠU = *kubšu*, which he translated as “Mütze” (cap), for headgear.¹² For the second mill. BC, he deemed it possible that the foreign word *huli(y)am* designated a helmet.¹³ However, this word is not attested in the Middle Assyrian documentation.

The assumption that Assyrian infantry and cavalry men used helmets seems to be supported by the iconography in reliefs and seal impressions.¹⁴ A more problematical task is to assign a word to the helmets represented. In spite of Salonen’s misgivings, some recent dictionaries translate the word *qurpi(s)su(m)*, *qursi(p)pu(m)* as “helmet”.¹⁵ Four helmets (*qurpisū*) made of bronze are attested in a fragmentary unpublished document from Assur in relation to the palace of Adad-nārārī I (1295-1264 BC).¹⁶

How did a helmet look like? Would it have been as the worn by the soldiers represented at the pedestal of Tukulti-Ninurta I, according to the reconstruction by Moortgat-Correns?¹⁷ Or like the one depicted on the seal of Ilī-padā?¹⁸ The Assyrian helmet (*qurpisu*) was possibly conical, as it is shown in the representations of Asiatic helmets in Egyptian tombs of the period.¹⁹

The word *kubšu* “cap” is more common in the Middle Assyrian documentation. The Middle Assyrian caps were made of felt (*taḥapšu*).²⁰ The weight of the caps was not standardised. Six white caps weighed altogether two minas (ca. 1 kg), which means a weight of 166.6 g each.²¹ On the other hand, another document reports that 310 caps

12. Wilcke 1972-1975, p. 311-313.

13. *AHw.* 353-354, “Helm”; *CAD* H 228, “helmet”; Salonen 1965, p. 68, “Helm”; *CDA* 119a, “helmet”; Oppenheim 1950, p. 192 n. 16 and Wilcke 1972-1975, p. 312 suggest a Hurrian origin for this word; cf. Richter 2012, p. 162a, “Hurrität ungewiss”.

14. Moortgat-Correns 1988, p. 113, Abb. 2 (here mostly restored; is she influenced by the Neo-Assyrian representations?); Akkermans 1998, p. 253, fig. 10a.

15. *CDA* 291b; Parpola 2007, p. 32b, “helmet; hauberk”; previously Speiser 1950, p. 48b, suggested a Hurrian origin for this noun; Richter 2012, p. 228-229; Sasson 1969, p. 30 “helmet”. *CAD* Q 319 refers to *gurpisu*, *CAD* G 139, “leather hauberk covered with metal scales (as part of armour for soldiers and horses”; *AHw.* 929b “ein Panzerüberwurf mit Nackenschutz für Menschen und Pferde”; E. Salonen 1965, p. 101-104, was against the translation of helmet, as a *gurpisu* was also used for horses, and a horse cannot wear a helmet. He thought that it was armour protecting the horse’s neck. Referring to a soldier, it was protection for his chest. Consequently, he did not list it with other words meaning helmet on page 168, but with the words related to armour on page 169. See Kendall 1975, p. 189-190 “a leather helmet usually covered with metal scales; a suit of armour with head-piece attached; a piece of horse armour used to protect the animals head and neck”; definitively Kendall 1981, p. 201-231 for helmet.

16. Ass. 2001.D-1615: 6’ (courtesy of E. Frahm).

17. Moortgat-Correns 1988, p. 113, fig. 2.

18. Akkermans 1998, p. 253, fig. 10.

19. Kendall 1981, p. 215, fig 2; p. 216, fig. 3; p. 219, fig. 5; p. 220, figs. 6-7.

20. *MARV* 3, 53: 1-2 (see Cancik-Kirschbaum 1999, p. 92; Postgate 2000, p. 214; Jakob 2003, p. 27-28); *MARV* 10, 17: 4. On this material see Cancik-Kirschbaum 1999, p. 85-87 and Postgate 2000, p. 213-217.

21. *MARV* 3, 5: 33; cited along with *šaḥarrātu*, *nakbusu*, see Jakob 2003, p. 417.

weight 46.5 minas (= ca. 23.25 kg), i.e. 75 g each. According to Postgate, the purpose of the latter was to equip “footsoldiers or similar” (*ḥupšūtu*).²² A cap (?) along with a coat (*naḥlaptu*) and an *išḥanabe*-cloth are given as a present to an interpreter of the Hittite language.²³ Other attestations of *kubšu* appear either in highly damaged contexts or in unpublished texts.²⁴

The question of how we should imagine what an Assyrian cap (*kubšu*) was like during this period remains unclear. Would it have been like the one that can be seen on the seal of Ušur-namkūr-šarri?²⁵ Or like the one represented on the seal of the official Aššur-rēša-iši?²⁶ Possibly from this designation we can rule out the one represented on a pyxis of Tukulti-Ninurta I's reign²⁷ and the one on the seal of Ezbu-lēšir on a receipt,²⁸ which both belong to the category “crown” (*agū*).

1.2. Armour

According to Dezsö, armour was worn by warriors riding on chariots. They could not hold a shield for defence, because they needed both hands for the battle.²⁹ The word *kurs/šimtu* designating armour scale is not attested in Middle Assyrian, but armour scales have been found in e.g. Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta.³⁰ Neither is the poetical word *aplūhtu* for armour attested in Middle Assyrian, or derives from the root **hlp* “clad in”,³¹ other than *naḥlaptu*, a kind of coat.³²

The Middle Assyrian word for armour found in the archival documentation is **sariu* which, according to *AHw.*, is a Hurrian loanword.³³ But most of the Middle Assyrian attestations refer to the leatherworker (*aškāp sariāni*) who was in charge of producing them.³⁴ Two sticks (sing. *ḥattu*) of felt weighing 16 minas (8 kg, i.e. 4 kg

22. *MARV* 3, 53: 1-3, see Postgate 2000, p. 214.

23. *MARV* 3, 12: 1-4 with *naḥlaptu* and *išḥanabe*; Freydank 1994, p. 31-33 did not attempt a translation but read ^{TUG}UGU?; Postgate 2000, p. 214, *kupšu* “a hat”; followed by Jakob 2003, p. 542, who translates “Mütze?”; Gaspa 2012, p. 407 reads ^{TUG}UGU and translates “headgear”.

24. Damaged context: Ass. 2001.D-2357: 4'; *MARV* 5, 82: 2'; unpublished Tab T05A-36: 16 (courtesy of D. Shibata).

25. Fischer 1999, p. 129, fig. 1.

26. *Ibid.*, p. 131, fig. 5.

27. Orthmann 1974, fig. 255a.

28. Seal no. 5 on *MARV* 8, 22; see there pl. 2.

29. Dezsö 2003-2005, p. 319; see previously Yadin 1963, p. 84, p. 196 and Kendall 1975, p. 263.

30. Eickhoff 1985, p. 90 and pl. 14 (T 340).

31. Apart from the Epic of Tukulti-Ninurta, which is written in Babylonian, Machinist 1978, p. 120-121, 46, *taḥlīpu* (*CAD* T 51a, “plating, armour (of infantry and war chariots)”).

32. Postgate 2001, p. 377, “coat”; Michel, Veenhof 2010, p. 227, 236-237, “cloak”. See below note 43 on Ass. 2001.D-2359.

33. Salonen 1965, p. 105-107; *CAD* S 313, “leather coat, often reinforced with metal pieces”; Kendall 1975, p. 263-286, “Specifically, however, *sariam* described a type of body armour which was almost entirely lamellar or cataphractic construction, consisting of a woollen or leather base fabric to which were sewn as many overlapping rows of metal scales as would completely cover the undergarment and provide for its weaver a nearly impenetrable yet flexible metal skin” (p. 263); foreign word; *AHw.* 1029b, “Panzer(hemd)” (from Hurrian, citing Speiser 1950, p. 47-48; see also Oppenheim 1950, p. 193). Cf. G. Wilhelm *apud* Waetzoldt 1990, p. 26 n. 148 doubts that *sariam* is a Hurrite loanword; Richter 2012, p. 357-358, “Hurritität ungewiss”.

34. Jakob 2003, p. 436-441; Kendall 1975, p. 90 rightly translates “leatherworker and armourer”.

each) for the king's chariot are under the responsibility of the official of the leatherworkers of the armours.³⁵ Leatherworkers of the armour are listed among people from (?) the Kašiyari area.³⁶

According to the information above, armour (**sariu*) was made of leather with bronze scales sewn on it.³⁷ This kind of armour might have been inspired by Mittanian models, but it was not very different from that used by other armies of the period.³⁸ Apparently, soldiers did not necessarily wear armour from the start of the campaign, or during the long foot marches, but put it on in the battlefield directly before combat; this is indicated by the report from a delivery note in which barley is given for the one hundred donkeys transporting armour to the battlefield.³⁹ In the Epic of Tukulti-Ninurta, the bravery of the Assyrian warriors is exalted through a reference to the fact that they entered battle without wearing armour.⁴⁰

The specific use of armour by soldiers, horses or chariots is not clearly attested in the Middle Assyrian documentation.⁴¹ If the restoration of the word (*sariam*) in a diplomatic letter is correct, Adad-nārārī I (or Shalmaneser I) may have sent armour to Hattusili III as a present.⁴² Finally, pieces of armour are listed among uniforms in a document from Assur.⁴³

1.3. Shields

Shields (sing. *arittu*) were used by the Middle Assyrian army. As in the case of armour, leather was the most important material used for their production.⁴⁴ Ox hides are attested as being used for this purpose.⁴⁵ Specialised leatherworkers (*aškāp ariāte*) were responsible for their production.⁴⁶ But other materials were also used, such as a red dye (wool?) (*hurhurātu*).⁴⁷

35. MARV 3, 59: 6, *rab aškāp sariāni* (Jakob 2003, p. 436-441).

36. MARV 2, 27: III? 18' (in highly damaged context), VI 7'.

37. Speiser 1950, p. 47; Kendall 1975, p. 263.

38. Deszö 2003-2005, p. 319-323, with the previous bibliography.

39. MARV 8, 51 (related to MARV 1, 1 IV 43).

40. *sa-ri-ia-ma-a-ti ul it-taḥ-li-pu la-biš i-dak-[ku (x)]* "They were not clothed in body armour, (but) like lions they kill", Machinist 1978, p. 110-111, 39'; see also 120-121, 46 (*taḥlipu*).

41. MARV 3, 59 may indicate the use of armour for chariots.

42. *KBo* 1, 14: 25'; *CAD* S 314; Götze 1940, p. 28; Faist 2001, p. 23; Wilhelm 2006, p. 239; cf. Hagenbuchner 1989, p. 268 is unsure about the restoration; Harrak 1987, p. 71 does not restore; Mora, Giorgieri 2004, no. 1, do not restore *sariam* because of lack of room on the line.

43. Ass. 2001. D-2359 I 10'; highly damaged context; with a coat (*nahlaptu*) and *hullānu*-clothes; Frahm 2002, p. 84-85.

44. The determinative for leather products (KUŠ) usually accompanies this noun: ^{KUŠ}*a-ri-a-te*, *KAJ* 5: 5.6.11 (*AHw*. 68b, 1.b; *CAD* A/II 269b, 1); ^{KUŠ}*a-ri-tu*, BM 122637+: 3'. 10' (Millard 1970, pl. 33); ^{KUŠ}*a-ri-tu*, *MARV* 10, 6: 23'. According to the documentation from Nuzi, they are made of leather and copper; Kendall 1975, p. 175.

45. *MARV* 10, 22.

46. *KAJ* 5: 5 (Jakob 2003, p. 436); *MARV* 4, 50 r.' 5' (Postgate 2008, p. 89); *MARV* 10, 22: 7.

47. (Barley) *a-na ši-pār pi-ir-ki ša hu-ur-hu-ra-te ša a-ri-a-te*, "(barley given to two people) for the work on the red *pirku* of the shields", *MARV* 8, 21: 16-18 ("*pirku* might refer to the frame of the shield; maybe it's transversal part, if we link the word to *CAD pirku* B; in all cases "...red *pirku* of the shields" seems to me a better translation", courtesy of P. Abrahami).

The documentation currently available does not report, whether other materials such as wood (as in Nuzi) were used,⁴⁸ but some kind of other, more rigid, material was probably necessary as a frame or surface of the shield.

Specialised troops bore the shields in the battle (*šābū ša arâte*).⁴⁹ This might indicate that they were subordinate to the protection of other fighting units, as attested for the Neo-Assyrian period.⁵⁰ As no representations or remains of Middle Assyrian shields have been found, we have no evidence regarding their form or size.

Shields could be taken as booty and brought to the capital city, Assur.⁵¹ Leather shields are listed along with wine skins, chests with large jars, sheep, oxen, tin, copper and horses in a document which has been described as a “tribute” list or a list of presents from governors and client rulers.⁵²

A couple of passages that mention shields remain problematic because of the contexts. In a rations list from Šibanibe (Tell Billa), five litres of bread for the temple of Adad are placed (?) before the shields (*ša IGI a-ra-a-te*).⁵³ Given that the mention of the “people of the shields” (above) also occurs in a rations list from the same city, these two passages may be related and refer to soldiers bearing shields; i.e. *ša pān arâte* may be a synonym for this kind of troop.⁵⁴

2. Offensive weapons

Weapons used for close quarters combat were the stick, the whip, the mace, the dagger, the sword and the axe. (Of course, I am aware of the arbitrariness of the classification between close and distance combat weapons, because, for example, an axe – here classified as a weapon used at close quarters – could be thrown. The same argument is true for a lance or a spear, which could also either be thrust or thrown).

48. Kendall 1975, p. 175.

49. Billa 41: 2; Jakob 2003, p. 214, “Schildtruppen”.

50. They often appear accompanying the bowmen; *CAD A/II*, 270, 2, “shield bearer”; Schrakamp 2009a, p. 178a; see e.g. the Tiglath-pileser III, Barnett, Falkner 1962, pl. 12, 28, 32, 40, 52, 55, 73-77; reliefs of Sargon II in Dūr-Šarrukīn, Botta 1849-1850, pl. 60, 62; reliefs of Assurbanipal, Barnett 1976, pl. 16, pl. 21 slab 15, pl. 26 slab 17, pl. 71 m; cf. Kendall 1975, p. 175 “carried by all of the various types of warriors”; Jakob 2003, p. 214.

51. ^{r.7)}[...] *a-ri-a-te-šu-nu* (...) ⁸⁾[...] x *a-na* ^{URU}*Aš+šur ub-I*[a...], “he brought their shields [...] to Assur”, *MARV* 5, 80 (historical text, Tiglath-Pileser I).

52. BM 122637+; 3. 10' (Millard 1970, pl. 33; 12th or 11th century BC) (see discussion in Llop 2015, p. 258-261). Bronze shields as tribute are also attested in the royal inscriptions of Aššur-nāšir-apli II (883-859 BC), ZABAR *ša a-ri-a-te*, RIMA 2, A.0.101.1: 75 and 17: 96. Sargon took shields of gold, silver and copper as booty from Urartu to Assyria: *TCL* 3, 370, 379, 392 (*CAD A/II*, 269, 1.a.2').

53. Billa 43: 4, passage not included in the dictionaries; Finkelstein 1953, p. 132, note a: “which (are to be placed) before the shields”, i.e. shields suspended in the temple.”

54. Is the expression *ina pān arâte*, *MARV* 10, 86: 4 in a damaged context; related hereto?

2.1 Sticks/clubs, whips, maces

2.1.1 Sticks

Sticks appear in the Middle Assyrian archival documentation with a functional purpose; they are used as holders for felt (*MARV* 3, 57: 1; 59: 1) or other materials.⁵⁵ The same word for stick (*ḥattu*) can designate the royal sceptre,⁵⁶ or the power insignia of an official.⁵⁷

But a stick (*ḥattu* = ^{GI5}PA) could be used as a weapon.⁵⁸ In fact, according to the Middle Assyrian laws, the stick was the instrument used to inflict punishments, when the felon was sentenced to receive blows.⁵⁹

A stick could certainly be used as a weapon as shown by a letter report from Dūr-katlimmu (Cancik-Kirschbaum 1996, no. 16):

1-2) [To] Aššur-[iddin], my lord (say): “[Tablet] of Šulmu, [your] servant.

3-4) I prostrate myself. I stay at the service of my lord.

5- 8) The iron, which my lord gave me to produce arrow(-tip)s – I have made twenty arrow(-tip)s from it.

9-15) The iron-plate, which my lord gave to me to produce a stick, is not suitable to produce a stick.

16-19a) Today, Šamaš-šezibanni has required from me: “I want to do an alloy for arrow(-tip)s (with it)”.

19b-21) Without (the permission) of my lord, I fear to give (it). According to what my lord will write to me, (I should do).

22-25) The small iron(-plate), which my lord gave to me, is not suitable to produce a whip(grip).

26-30) They have opened (?) the [...]... on the 5th day. There was no iron. ...[as much (iron) as] there is in [your] sphere of responsibility.

31-32) (damaged).

Lines 9-15 of this letter suggest a stick lined with iron which could be used as a weapon, as also implied by the presence of arrow(tip)s in the same letter.⁶⁰ Another (made of?/lined with?) iron-stick is attested in an, unpublished, damaged list of military items from Assur.⁶¹

55. *MARV* 8, 14: 2; ÉPHÉ 444: 8' (Durand 1982, pl. 84); both attestations in damaged context.

56. E.g. the scepter of Shalmaneser I (Kühne, Röllig 1989, pl. 51); *MVAG* 41/3, 12: 35 = 12'.

57. *MVAG* 41/3, 14: 9; Billa 6: 15 here? Cf. Jakob 2003, p. 144.

58. *CAD* H 155, 3.b; Stol 2012, p. 192a.

59. *CAD* H 155, 3.; e.g. MA laws: (*KAV* 1 II 90, § 19); I 7 § 7; II 78 § 18; II 103 § 21; V 75, 81, 100 § 40; *KAV* 2 IV 18 B § 8; IV 26 B § 9; IV 32 B § 10; V 32 B § 14; *KAV* 6 + 143: 5 C+G § 8; 24 C + G § 10; *AfO* 12, Taf. 6, 2: 4. Stol 2012, p. 192a. See also ¹¹⁾(...) *ḥa-mu-su 1 me 1 šu-ši* ^{GI5}PA^{MES 12)} *i-ta-ḥa-šu-né*, “They have been pinched. They (the thieves) have received 160 blows with a rod”, TSA 96-15: 11 (courtesy of F.A.M. Wiggermann). Note that this punishment is also attested in Nuzi, cf. HSS 13 184 (courtesy of P. Abrahami).

60. Stol 2012, p. 192a.

61. 1 PA ša AN.BAR, Ass.2001.D-2217 r. 8' (courtesy of E. Frahm).

Wooden sticks were used for the production of bows⁶² (see below) and, possibly, shields.⁶³ So it is no surprise to find then sticks of *kiškināu*-wood kept in a storehouse.⁶⁴

A group of people equipped/armed with sticks (*ša ḥuṭāri = ša* ^{GIŠPA^{MEŠ}}) is attested in our documentation, but their role is still unclear.⁶⁵ A couple of attestations come from documents which are too damaged to be relevant.⁶⁶

2.1.2 Whips

The whip (*maḥittu*)⁶⁷ is rarely attested in the Middle Assyrian documentation, and no evidence is available for its use as a weapon. Its mention after arrow(-tip)s and an iron-stick in the letter above (BATSH 4, 16: 28) implies this use. In other places, the whip is related to the chariot.⁶⁸

2.1.3 Maces

It is dubious whether maces (sing. *kakku* = ^{GIŠ}TUKUL) were used as a weapon during the Middle Assyrian period.⁶⁹ Although, Salonen reminds us that originally *kakku* designated a mace,⁷⁰ we observe that the noun *kakku* is translated as “stick, weapon” and not “mace” by the standard dictionaries.⁷¹

Moreover, with the noun *kakku*, there is the problem of distinguishing between its meanings of “weapon” and “tool”.⁷² This second meaning seems clear in the next example:

naggāra u pir'a kannamari arḥiṣ lūblūne kakka ammar ibaššiūni lūblūne “May they send a woodworker and an apprentice hither quick in the morning. May they bring as much (many) tool(s) as is (are) (available)” (Jakob 2009, no. 1: 4-7; TCH 90.G.23: 4-8 cited also in Jakob 2003, p. 108 n. 237).

But *kakku* is also attested as a general designation for weapon, e.g.: [...*til*]-*pa-ni kakki ša tidūki*, “a composite bow, weapon of combat”.⁷³ In fact, the maces/weapons of gods are mentioned in the royal inscriptions of the period.⁷⁴ They appear in the Middle Assyrian coronation ritual: *agā ša Aššur u kakkē ša* ^d*Ninlil inaššia*, “he brings

62. ^{GIŠ}PA *ša kiškināe*, Ass.2001.D-2218: 3'9:15:21; 26'; see Frahm 2002, p. 75-80, see particularly the commentary on pages 78-79.

63. See above and CAD H 156a, *sub ša ḥatti* (a type of shield).

64. 1 ^{GIŠ}PA *ša ki-iš-ka-na-e*, KAJ 310: 48 f., (for pegs) and see lines 49, 53, 56, 58 (CAD H, 155a; Postgate 1988, no. 50).

65. *ša* ^{GIŠ}PA^{MEŠ}, MARV 4, 33: 9, 21; MARV 2, 17: 54, 68; see Deller 1987, p. 59b; as a title used by persons, MARV 4, 102 iii 8'; MARV 4, 74: 39-40, *kaššiu ša ḥuṭāri*; MARV 2, 17 fragm. 6: 5'; Assur 3, 3: 9 (AO 19227 = Ass 11017d2; NA MZL 333 no. 464; “Stabträger” see Jakob 2003, p. 223; Mayer 2011, p. 356.

66. MARV 4, 48: 5'; MARV 6, 22: 1'.

67. The noun *qinnazu* for whip has not been attested until now in Middle Assyrian (CAD Q 256-257). In general, see Waetzoldt 2003-2005, p. 382-386; Deller, Mayer 1984, p. 76, with Neo-Assyrian attestations.

68. See attestations in CAD M/I 103; and MARV 9, 56: 13 (in damaged context).

69. Edzard 1976-1980, p. 578-579. According to Waetzoldt 1990, p. 8, maces were of no importance in the Ebla army during the third mill. BC.

70. Salonen 1965, p. 155-157, “Stock; Waffe”; see also Sasson 1969, p. 28 “mace”.

71. CAD K 50, “weapon”; AHW. 422, “Stock; Waffe”; CDA 141, “stick, weapon”.

72. See already CAD K 56-57 under *kakku*, see commentary on page 57b.

73. Ass. 2001.D-2279: 5 (unpubl.; courtesy of E. Frahm); Frahm 2002, p. 82-83.

74. Aššur, Anu and Enlil, RIMA 1, A.0.76.3:21; Aššur, RIMA 1, A.0.76.21.9'; A.0.77.1: 15; Ištar, RIMA 1, A.0.76.1001: 10' (interestingly always in plural).

the crown of Aššur and the weapons of Ninlil” (MVAG 41/3, 10: 15’) and also in the archival documentation: *ilānu belū kakkē ana ekalli ērubūne*, “The gods, the lords of the weapons entered the palace” (MARV 2, 7: 3-5); [...] ^d*a-šur* ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES} x x [...], “the god Aššur...the weapons” (MARV 10, 4: 17’ in a fragmentary context); and the god mace/weapon (^d*Kakku*) is also attested (Deller 1987, p. 59a).

The mace/weapon of the king is, of course, present in the royal inscriptions: *aš-šur EN a-na pa-la-ḫi-šu ki-niš ú-ta-ni-ma a-na šu-šur* SAG.GE₆.A ^{GIS}PA ^{GIS}TUKUL *ù ši-bir-ra id-di-na* “When Aššur, the lord, faithfully chose me to worship him, gave me the sceptre, weapon, and staff to (rule) properly the black headed people (...)” (RIMA 1, A.0.77.1: 22-24).⁷⁵ This mace/weapon granted by the god Aššur was not an abstract idea as a couple of administrative documents from Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta show.⁷⁶ According to these documents, at least one of them should be dated after the reign of Ninurta-apil-ekur (1181-1169 BC), red-dyed wool (*tabarribu*) with no clearly specified function, was issued for the maces/weapons of the previous deceased monarchs Ērišum I, Aššur-nādin-ahhē I, Shalmaneser I and Tukulti-Ninurta I. From these documents, Cancik-Kirschbaum concludes that the maces/weapons of deceased Assyrian kings were kept together in the “palace of the weapons” (*ekal kakkē*) in the Old Palace of Assur and were worshipped there.⁷⁷

From the evidence above, it is difficult to discern what kind of troops the “ones of the maces/weapons” (*šābū ša kakkē*) mentioned in a letter from Dūr-Katlimmu (BATSH 4, 8: 38) might be. Due to the opposition to chariot troops (ĒRIN^{MES} DUMU^{MES} SIG₃) in the same letter, Jakob (2003, p. 215) supposes that it was an infantry force.⁷⁸ Note that this hypothesis is supported by a Neo-Assyrian passage in the inscriptions of Sennacherib (704-681 BC) when he describes the forces (*kišir šarrūtīya*) sent against the king of Elam as “soldiers (ĒRIN.ḪI.A ^{GIS}TUKUL), chariots (and) horses”.⁷⁹ The noun *kakku* also appears in the context of a chariot being repaired (MARV 10, 25: 14).

75. See also the following passages in the royal inscriptions of Tiglath-pileser I: *ša d a-šur* ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES} *š-šu ú-ša-ḫi-lu-ma*, “(Tiglath-pileser I) whose weapons the god Aššur has sharpened”, RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 i 36-37 (CAD Š/IL, 276a); ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES} *š-šu-nu dan-nu-ti a-bu-ub tam-ḫa-ri qa-ti lu-šat-me-ḫu*, “they (Aššur and the great gods) placed in my hands their mighty weapons, deluge in battle”, RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 i 49-51; *ša i-na pa-an* ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES} *ia ip-pár-ši-du*, “(troops) who had fled from my weapons”, RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 i 85-86 also ii 2-3, ii 63, iii 13, v 55; *ša d a-šur EN* ^{GIS}TUKUL *dan-na mu-šék-niš la-a ma-gi-ri ú-šat-me-ḫu-ma*, “the god Aššur, my lord, had placed in my hand the strong weapon which subdues the insumissive”, RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 ii 97-98; ^d*nin-urta ú* ^dIGI.DU ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES} *š-šu-nu ez-zu-te ú* ^{GIS}BAN-su-nu *šir-ta a-na i-di EN-ti-ia iš-ru-ku*, “The gods Ninurta and Nergal gave me their fierce weapons and their exalted bow for my lordly arms”, RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 vi 58-60; *ša i-na ti-ib* ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES} *š-šu ez-zu-ú-te tu-bu-qa-at er-bit-ta uš-ra-ab-bu-ma*, “who by the attack of his fierce weapons has caused the four corners (of the world) to quake”, RIMA 2, A.0.87.4: 8-9, similarly 10: 9-10.

76. MARV 4, 138 and 140; see edition and commentary by Cancik-Kirschbaum 2012, p. 33-49, with the previous bibliography. Perhaps, we should read, 1 *ma-na* SÍG.ZA.GÍN SA₃ *ki-mu ta-bar-ri-^rbē^r a-na 1 TUKUL ša(?)* BĀRA. MARV 1, 24: 9’; cf. CAD T 22, a.4’ and 72, c.3’; with two alternative readings.

77. RIMA 2, A.0.87.4: 72-76; Pedde, Lündstrom 2008, p. 172-173; Cancik-Kirschbaum 2012, p. 46; cf. CAD T 281 reading ^{GIS}TÚG^{MES} instead of ^{GIS}TUKUL^{MES}.

78. Cf. Sasson 1969, p. 25 translates “well equipped group”. See *šāb kakki* in CAD K 55 c. “troops”, 2.

79. OIP 2, 87: 29 (CAD K 55b); cited also by Jakob 2003, p. 216 n. 103.

2.2 Knives, daggers, swords

These three objects (which are different to us) have a single correspondence in Middle Assyrian: *patru*.

The knives listed as the property of deported families in Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta were possibly not used as weapons, as they are among other property of these families such as domestic animals, stools and beds,⁸⁰ but a military use cannot be ruled out, as the heads of these families were archers at the service of the Assyrian army.

Daggers or swords (GÍR^{ME5}) are attested in a report of materials (principally metals or metal objects) delivered to artisans from Assur.⁸¹ Four daggers made of bronze and one made of iron are listed along with an *ulmu*-axe in an inventory from Assur which also records garments and shoes.⁸² According to J.N. Postgate, (unpaid) dagger-pommels (*ka-ri ša* GÍR^{ME5}) are attested in a debt-note from Assur.⁸³

According to Middle Assyrian documentation, most knives/swords were made of bronze.⁸⁴ Iron daggers/swords are only attested twice, in an inventory⁸⁵ and in a diplomatic letter. In the latter, a Hittite king (Hattušil III or Tudhaliya IV) is sending an iron dagger-blade to the Assyrian monarch (Adad-nārārī I or Shalmaneser I) as a present.⁸⁶

One of the bronze swords from the period has survived.⁸⁷ Interestingly, it bears the following engraved inscription: “(Property of) the palace of Adad-nārārī (I), king of the totality, son of Arik-dēn-ili, king of Assyria, son of Enlil-nārārī (who was) also king of Assyria”⁸⁸

2.3 Axes, battleaxes

The axe presents a similar problem to the previous objects, that is, whether it was used for peaceful or warlike purposes. The following designations for axe are available in Middle Assyrian: *ḥaššinnu*, *pāšu*, **pāltu* (see the dictionaries under *pāštu*), *ulmu* and *kalāpu*.⁸⁹

80. *MARV* 2, 6 II 12, 1 GÍR UD.KA.BAR along with an axe and four chairs; II 31, *idem*, along with an axe and cart; II 60, *idem* along with five pigs and a table; V 82, 2 GÍR UD.KA.BAR, along with an axe and a chair; *MARV* 4, 89 II 45*, 1 GÍR UD.KA.BAR.

81. GÍR UD.KA.BAR 1 GÍR ŠĀ (?), *MARV* 10, 3: 12, 45; they must be a weapon because of the presence of bows and arrows in the same document.

82. Postgate 1973, pl. 13, no. 1: 10-11; Freydank, Saporetta 1989, p. 46, 84, translate “Dolch”.

83. *KAJ* 112: 3 = Postgate 1988, no. 67, “dagger-pommels”; see Salonen 1965, p. 58; *AHW* 450, 2, “Schwertknauf”; *CAD* K 221, a.2; *CDA* 149b.

84. See the references on note 80 and furthermore GÍR^{ME5} UD.KA.BAR, Ass. 2001.D-1320a: 3; GÍR [UD]. KA.BAR, *Billa* 65: 32; GÍR UD[.KA.BAR] line 33, in a highly damaged letter.

85. Postgate 1973, pl. 13, no. 1: 11, see above note 80.

86. EME GÍR AN.BAR “an iron dagger-blade”, *KBo* 1, 14: 23; Götze 1940, p. 29; Faist 2001, p. 22-25, “eine Schwertklinge aus Eisen”; Mora, Giorgieri 2004, no. 1, “una lama di coltello in ferro”; Wilhelm 2006, p. 238, “eine Dolchklinge aus Eisen”.

87. It can be seen on the CDLI web site (no. CDLI P393600).

88. É.GAL 110-ÉRIN.TÁḤ MAN KIŠ A GÍD-DI-DINGIR MAN KUR *aš+šur* A 4BAD-ÉRIN.TÁḤ MAN KUR *aš+šur-ma*, *RIMA* 1, A.0.76.0.41.07; see Schrakamp 2010, p. 449-450.

89. *Akkullu* (translated as “hatchet, pick(axe)” in *CDA* 10a; cf. the other dictionaries) is, until now, only attested in the royal inscriptions and its function is that one of a tool. Salonen 1965 does not include it in his study.

The noun *ḥaššinnu* seems to be the generic designation for axe.⁹⁰ It is one that anybody could have at home, as it appears among the inventories of the household equipment of deported Subarean families in Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta.⁹¹ The delivery of an axe (*ḥaššinnu*) belonging to the palace to a Katmuhean gardener suggests that the function of this tool may have been peaceful.⁹²

Middle Assyrian axes were made of bronze:

5 *ḥa-ši-nu* UD.KA.BAR, *MARV* 4, 111: 2;

1 *ḥa-ši-na* UD.KA.BAR, *KAJ* 121a: 5;⁹³

[1 *ḥ*]a-ši-na U[D.KA.BAR], *MARV* 8, 86: 1;

1 *ḥa-ši-nu* UD.KA.BAR, see note 91;

1 *ḥa-ši-nu*, *MARV* 10, 37: 3; along with other objects made of bronze.

They weighed between half (250 g)⁹⁴ and one mina (500 g).⁹⁵

The military use of axes is supported by an agreement between two people on the sharing of the expenses referring to a war chariot in which an axe (*ḥaššinnu*) appears along with an *ulmu*-axe.⁹⁶ This use may also be supported by a delivery note stating that fifty axes were cast on the day the king (Tiglath-pileser I) went to Mušri.⁹⁷ On the other hand, a commercial aim has recently been proposed for this expedition.⁹⁸

The *pāšu*-axe⁹⁹ appears in Middle Assyrian mostly related to the trade of a woodworker (*naggār pāše*; lit. woodworker of the *pāšu*-tool).¹⁰⁰ For this reason, this might be an adze.¹⁰¹ The woodworkers using this tool appear working at the construction of Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta (*MARV* 2, 17: 100) and in naval construction (*MARV* 4, 34: 12'). In the Middle Assyrian laws, a *pāšu*-axe is used to cut the lower lip of a man who has kissed a married woman (*KAV* 1 I 95; § 9).¹⁰² Until now, this tool has not appeared related to the military in the Middle Assyrian documentation.¹⁰³ The attestation of *pāšu*-axes in a note of partial payment for a field is possibly a misreading.¹⁰⁴

90. It is also the oldest: Sumerian *ḥa-zi*, *ḥa-zi-in*; Salonen 1965, p. 14-16.

91. 1 *ḥa-ši-n[u]*, *MARV* 2, 6 I 27'; 1 *ḥa-ši-nu*, II 12 (listed along with 105 sheep and goats, three pigs, a bronze knife, four stools, a table and four beds); II 24 (along with domestic animals and one stool); II 52 (along with domestic animals, a bronze knife, a wagon, beds, four stools, two tables); 2 *ḥa-š[i-nu]* (?...), III 8 (along with domestic animals, a bronze caldron, four stools, a table); V 53'; *ḥ*]a-ši-nu; V 82'' (damaged context); 1 *ḥa-ši-nu*; VI 11 (along with domestic animals, a stool and a bed).

92. 1 *ḥa-ši-nu*¹ UD.KA.BAR 1 *ma-na* KILLÁ ša É.GAL-*lim* ša ŠU PN, *KAJ* 298: 1-4 = *MARV* 3, 67; Ass. 21101ay.

93. Postgate 1988, no. 75.

94. 50 *ḥa-ši-ni ša ½ ma-na*.TA.ÀM *i+na*^{URU}Aš+šur šap-ka, *KAJ* 249 = *MARV* 10, 44: 11-13.

95. 1 *ḥa-ši-nu* UD.KA.BAR 1 *ma-na* KILLÁ, *KAJ* 298 = *MARV* 3, 67: 1-2. A weight between 1-2 minas is also mentioned by Mayer 2003, p. 373, with previous bibliography.

96. *ul-ma ù ḥa-ši-na*, *KAJ* 307: 10; see edition by Postgate 1982, p. 306.

97. See note 94.

98. See Prechel, Freydank 2011, p. 6 *sub* no. 44.

99. Salonen 1965, p. 20-21 "eine Art Axt"; *AHw.* 846 "Beil, Axt"; *CAD* P 267b, (an ax or hatchet); *CDA* 270 "axe, adze".

100. Jakob 2003, p. 449, "Beil-Schreiner".

101. *CDA* 270.

102. See Saporetti 1982a, p. 63; Saporetti 1984, p. 94; Roth 1995, p. 157; *CAD* P 267b.

103. Cf. Sasson 1969, p. 29, in Mari they were part of the equipment of soldiers.

104. *KAJ* 257: 4.6; Ismail-Sabir 1967, no. 69: 4.6, *pa-še*; *AHw.* 846b, 1. (line 6, 1 *pa-še*); cf. *CAD* P 268b, in *KAJ* 257: 6 read (tin) ŠAM 2 (BÁN) ŠE (see *bitrumu* disc. section); *CAD* B 282a.

Hardly anything is known about the **pāltu*-axe in Middle Assyrian (it should be **pāltu* in singular in Middle Assyrian).¹⁰⁵ Several *pāšātu*-axes are mentioned in an unpublished document from Assur (Ass.2001.D-2275b: 2).¹⁰⁶

The noun *ulmu* seems to be a Hurrian loanword into Akkadian.¹⁰⁷ It has been translated as “axe”¹⁰⁸ and “lance, spear”.¹⁰⁹ The equivalence of *ulmu* and *qulmû* (axe) in the *malku*-list of synonyms favours the former translation.¹¹⁰ Note that a *qulmû* is used e.g. for felling trees (CAD Q 299, c) which is not conceivable for a spear or a lance.

A bronze *ulmu*-axe is loaned and will be given back on the return of the campaign (*ḥurādu*).¹¹¹ Another *ulmu* made of *ḥabalginnu*-alloy is listed with four bronze dagger/swords and one made of iron.¹¹² According to Cancik-Kirschbaum, this kind of alloy contained iron,¹¹³ whereas Reiter proposed identifying it with the magnetite.¹¹⁴ An *ulmu*-axe and a *ḥaššinnu*-axe are mentioned among the weapons belonging to the equipment of a war chariot.¹¹⁵ All this proves the military use of this weapon. *ulmu*-axes are mentioned in highly damaged and unpublished documents from Assur.¹¹⁶

A pickaxe (*kalāpu*)¹¹⁷ was an instrument or weapon after which a kind of soldier in Neo-Assyrian period was named.¹¹⁸ This instrument is attested already in the Middle Assyrian documentation. The house of a guilty person (*ḥi-ta ša LUGAL i+na-áš-ši*) is marked with a pickaxe (MARV 4, 151: 55-57). This tool is listed in an inventory among other metal instruments (Ass. 2001.D-1926).¹¹⁹ Ten pickaxes belonging to the palace are given to Enlil-damqu (?) to obtain a metalworker and then return them (ÉPHÉ 479: 1).¹²⁰ The pickaxes were made of bronze.¹²¹

105. See under *pāštu* in the dictionaries. Salonen 1965, p. 19-20; *AHw.* 846a, “Beil, Axt”; CAD P 267 (an axt or hatchet); CDA 270 “axe, adze”. The contact št results in *lt* in Middle Assyrian, GAG § 30 g; Mayer 1971, § 21. 8.

106. Frahm 2002, p. 81.

107. See Watson 1998, with literature; Richter 2012, p. 485.

108. Salonen, 1965, p. 22-23, “eine Art (Streit)axt(?); *AHw.* 1410b, “eine Axt”; CAD U/W 86a “ax”; CDA 421a, “axe”.

109. See the editions of *KAJ* 307 by Saporetto 1982b, p. 116 (“lancia”); Postgate 1982, p. 307 (“spear”); CAD H 134a (*sub ḥaššinnu*) “spear”; CAD P 33b (*sub paḥnu*) “lance”; contradicting itself; Postgate 2008, p. 89, “lance”; Schrakamp 2011, p. 631 among the nouns for spear and lance.

110. Hrůša 2010, p. 76 III 27, “eine Axt” and commentary on page 227. *AHw.* 927, “eine Axt”; CAD Q 299 “(an ax)”; CDA 290 “(kind of) axe”.

111. 1 *ul-mu š[a UD.KA.]BAR*, TR 2021+ 2051: 2; Saggs 1968, pl. 45; Postgate 1971, p. 499; not cited in CAD U/W, 86a; cf. *AHw.* 1410b.

112. 1 *ul-mu ša ḥa-bal-gi-ni*, Postgate 1973, pl. 13, no. 1: 12-13.

113. Cancik-Kirschbaum 1996, p. 173 *ad* 5.

114. Reiter 1997, p. 392-393, logogram AN.BAR GE_c.

115. *ul-ma ù ḥa-ši-na*, *KAJ* 307: 10; CAD U/W 56a. Various types of axes appear together in Old Babylonian documents: Mayer 2003, p. 372 (*ḥaššinnum* and *agalakkum*).

116. 20 *ul-ma-tu*, Ass. 2001.D-1320a: 7; Ass. 2001.D-1372: 2 (Frahm 2002, p. 65).

117. *AHw.* 424a, “Hacke, Picke”; CAD K 66a, (an ax); CDA 142a, “pickaxe”.

118. *AHw.* 425b “Meldereiter, Kurier”; CAD K 77b *sub kallābu*, “member of the light troops (a special military formation)”; CDA 142b *sub kallāpu* (a foot soldier).

119. Frahm 2002, p. 71-72

120. Durand 1982, pl. 84.

121. 1 [*ka-l*]a-*pu* UD.KA.BAR, *KAJ* 129: 2.

2.4 Spears, lances

There is a wide range of names for a weapon consisting of a long shaft ending in a metal tip: spears, lances, javelins, pikes. Some dictionaries have a difficulty distinguishing between a lance and a spear.¹²² Here I take the distinction made by I. Schrakamp (2011, p. 630). According to him, a spear was a short, light weapon meant to be slung or cast in distance combat, whereas a lance was heavier and used to thrusting in close fight.

In fact, contrarily to what one might expect, spears and lances appear rarely in the Middle Assyrian archival documentation and those that we do find are not free of problems. Designations attested for spear and lance are the following, arranged alphabetically:

Kutāḫu “lance”¹²³ is only attested as the personal name of an *alahḫenu* (baker?) of the Aššur temple.¹²⁴

The following two weapons are related, and both were used by the king in the royal hunt:

The *nar’amtū* has been defined differently by the dictionaries.¹²⁵ The existence of arrows (sing. *lištaḫū*) of *nar’amtū* shows that this weapon was not a mace and suggests that cast arrows.¹²⁶ It is mentioned in the context of royal sacrifices. This weapon is used by Aššur-bēl-kala to hunt lions (RIMA 2, A.0.89.7 iv 12). This is a further argument against the translation of “mace”; it was more probably a weapon used to thrust or to throw arrows, given the danger involved in hunting lions at close quarters.¹²⁷

The *pariangu* was another weapon used in royal hunting and related to the one just mentioned.¹²⁸ Tiglath-pileser I hunted a sea mammal (*nāḫīru*) with this instrument (RIMA 2, A.0.87.4: 67).¹²⁹ He reports that a *nāḫīru* was also called a sea-horse (ANŠE.KUR.RA ša A.AB.BA);¹³⁰ that is why some dictionaries translate *pariangu* as

122. The Duden German dictionary (Online):

Lanze: “aus einem langen Schaft und einer Spitze (aus Metall oder einem anderen harten Material) bestehende, für Stoß und Wurf bestimmte Waffe”.

Speer: “Waffe zum Stoßen oder Werfen in Form eines langen, dünnen, zugespitzten oder mit einer [Metall]spitze versehenen Stabes”.

These definitions are basically identical. The definitions in the Oxford dictionary are clearer:

Spear: “A thrusting or throwing weapon with a long shaft and a sharp-pointed usu. steel tip; a lance”.

Lance: “A spear with a long wooden shaft and an iron or steel head, held by a charging horseman”.

At Ebla, the distinction between spear and lance, was made through the designation (spear with the verb š u b “throw”) and the weight (a spear was heavier) Waetzoldt 1990, p. 2.

123. *AHw.* 517b, “eine schwere Lanze?”; *CAD* K 603 “(a lance)”; *CDA* 171 “spear, lance”; all only Neo-Assyrian.

124. Freydank 1991, p. 91.

125. *AHw.* 745b, “eine Waffe”; *CAD* N/I, 342a, “(a mace)”; *CDA* 241, “(a weapon, phps.) javelin”; not mentioned by Salonen 1965 or Schrakamp 2011, p. 631; cf. RIMA 2, A.0.89.7 iv 12, “a mace”; Streck 2002, p. 240, “eine Keule”.

126. $\Gamma_{16}^{7-GIS}LIS-ta-a-hu^{11}r\text{-}ša^{11}r\text{-}GIS\text{-}nār\text{-}'-am-ti^{127}r\text{-}a-na^{71}pa-ri-an-gi$, A 303 r. 10'-12'; cited by Freydank 1981, p. 458 and Freydank 1991, p. 167.

127. See the reliefs of Aššur-nāšir-apli II or Assurbanipal where he hunts lions with bow and arrows and spears; Barnett 1976, pls. VIII, X, XI, XII, XLIX; this is why the translation of *CDA* is to be preferred.

128. *AHw.* 833a, “eine Harpune”; *CAD* P 184, “(a weapon)”; *CDA* 266, “harpoon?”; Freydank 1981, p. 458 “Harpune”; RIMA 2, A.0.87.4: 67 “harpoon”.

129. See previously Weidner 1957-1958, p. 355 *ad* 67.

130. For the *nāḫīru* see *AHw.* 714 “Schnauber”; *CAD* N/I, 137 “whale”; Freydank 1981, p. 458 “eine Walart”; Briel-Chatonnet, Bordreuil 2000, p. 117-124, “l'hippopotame” Lundström 2012, p. 328-338.

“harpoon”. Tiglath-pileser I adds that he made this weapon himself (*epšet qātiya*), which may indicate a relative simple construction. This same weapon is possibly attested in an unpublished document from Assur along with the *nar’amtū* (A 303: 11; note 126). The mention of *pariangu* in a note about arrows for the king’s chariot during the reign of Tiglath-pileser I (*MARV* 1, 10: 7.10) is unclear, due to the damaged context in which it appears.¹³¹

Weapons for distance combat were the bow and arrows, and missiles thrown with a sling.

2.5 Bows, arrows, quivers

2.5.1 Bows

The weapon for distance combat *par excellence* was the bow.¹³² The word for bow is *qaštu*, Middle Assyrian **qaltu*, which, until now, only appears written logographically (GI⁵)PAN in our documentation.¹³³

Bow production is attested in the city of Assur in the Middle Assyrian period. The manual worker in charge of producing this weapon was the bowyer/bow-maker (*sasinnu* = LÚ.ZADIM).¹³⁴ The components of the bow were sinews (*gīdu*), glue (ŠE.ŠEN), *kiškanāu*-wood (CAD K 453) and ibex horns (sing. *turāḫū*).¹³⁵ Consequently, they were composite bows. It is not clear whether there was a specific denomination for the all wood bows.¹³⁶ An indication that most bows were composite during the Middle Assyrian period might be the fact that a specialist, the *sasinnu*, was in charge of their production, whereas in Ebla, for instance, the woodworker (NAGAR) was in charge of bow production.¹³⁷

131. See the interpretation of Freydank 1981, p. 458, who asks whether a *pariangu* is a tool for throwing a rope to the other side of a river to help in its crossing. Note that the use of a harpoon at the mount Ebih (Ġabal Ḥamrīn or Ġabal Makḫūl; Nashef 1982, p. 2 *sub* Abeḫ, and Ġabal Ḥamrīn, Parpola, Porter 2001, gazeteer page 8), the setting of this administrative document, would have little sense.

132. Postgate 2004, p. 456-458 has recently included Middle Assyrian evidence in his study on the bow and arrow. Sasson 1969, p. 25.

133. A possible syllabic writing might be found in a damaged context: *ša qa-al-t[e...]*, *MARV* 1, 53: 15; previously published by Weidner 1959, no. 49. For the change *št > lt*, see note 105.

134. Jakob 2003, p. 469-472. The profession *gelduḫlu* is translated by *CDA* 91b as a “bowyer, bowmaker” for the Middle Assyrian and Nuzi evidence; but contrast with *CAD* G, 60 *sub* *gelduḫlimma* “(a profession)” separated from *gelduḫlu* “(an official or craftsman)” and *AHw.* 284b *sub* *gelduḫlu*, *gelzu(h)lu*, “ein Beruf”. The evidence does not conclusively support the translation by *CDA*. Note also that both the Nuzi and the Middle Assyrian evidence already have the *sasinnu* in charge of making bows and arrows. See equivalence in *AHw.*; Mayer 1978, p. 186, discusses *keltuḫlu* and *sasinnu* together as bowmakers (“Bogenmacher”), *cf.* now Richter 2012, p. 206.

135. All these components appear in Ass.2001.D-2218; Frahm 2002, p. 75-80; sinews, glue and a third material broken away are present in *MARV* 3, 46: 4-6; Frahm 2002, p. 79 proposes that this third component was a set of horns.

136. *Cf.* Postgate 2004, p. 457.

137. Waetzoldt 1990, p. 7.

The bow is the king's weapon in the royal inscriptions (^{GIS}PAN *la-a šá-na-an*, "the unrivalled bow"),¹³⁸ given to him as a present by the gods.¹³⁹ The typical uses of the bow are combat¹⁴⁰ and hunting.¹⁴¹

In the archival documentation, bows are not directly attested as being used in combat. They appear in contracts of bow and arrow makers (sing. *sasinnu*), e.g. in a contract for the production of more than 14 bows without cases (*lā saḥpātu*) in two months (*MARV* 2, 32: 2.10). But they are usually just stored¹⁴² and listed in the inventories,¹⁴³ normally along with arrows.¹⁴⁴ They were taken from these stores¹⁴⁵ and given to different persons: e.g. a bow is given by the steward (*masennu*) to a Yidaean (*MARV* 10, 73: 1). Bows were also given as presents to foreign kings.¹⁴⁶ Twenty bows without cases (*lā saḥpātu*) are loaned, and a field is kept as guarantee for their return (*MARV* 1, 20).¹⁴⁷

Frahm observed that some bows are qualified as "of the king's hand" (*ša qāt šarri*) as distinct to the *ilku*-bows, i.e. bows of the service (*ša ilki*).¹⁴⁸ The difference implied by this distinction is difficult to ascertain. Frahm proposes a contrast in their users.¹⁴⁹ The former were used by the royal crack troops ("Kerntruppe"), whereas the latter were used by conscripts ("dienstverpflichtete Personen"). A difference in the quality of production is also conceivable. This difference in qualification is also observable for the arrows (see below).

Some parts of a bow are cited in the Middle Assyrian documentation. The bows could be produced or given without cases (*lā saḥpātu*). This means that some of them were produced with cases (sing. *siḥpu/seḥpu*),¹⁵⁰ which could be kept in a container (*bīt siḥpi*).¹⁵¹ The string of a bow is called *matnu*.¹⁵² Bows were delivered with their strings (sing. *adi matniša*)¹⁵³ which means that the reverse was also possible. According to Postgate, bows were kept unstrung when not used.¹⁵⁴

138. RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 vi 56 (Tiglath-pileser I).

139. ^dNIN.URTA ù ^dIGL.DU ^{GIS}TUKUL.MEŠ-*šu-nu ez-zu-te ù* ^{GIS}PAN-*su-nu šir-ta a-na i-di EN-ti-ia iš-ru-ku* "Ninurta and Nergal gave their fierce weapons and their exalted bow for my lordly arms", RIMA 2, A.0.87.1 vi 59 (Tiglath-pileser I).

140. It is not directly attested, but arrows kill enemies, RIMA 2, A.0.87.4 i 9.

141. AM.SI^{MEŠ} *ina* ^{GIS}PAN-*šu ú-šam-qit*, "he felled elephants with his bow", RIMA 2, A.0.89.7: 7-8 (Aššur-bēl-kala); see seal of Ninurta-tukul-Aššur on A 113; Donbaz 1976, pl. 23.

142. 55 bows, 450 arrows along with swords, gold, silver and clothes, are presents (NÍG.BA.MEŠ) in the *lušmu* house, *MARV* 10, 3: 11.12.

143. *KAJ* 310: 47.

144. "n+20 bows, arrows" in damaged context, *MARV* 9, 85: 1.

145. *KAV* 98: 46-47; letter of Bābu-aḥḥa-iddina, he orders to be chosen and brought to him.

146. Ass.2001.D-2279; Frahm 2002, p. 82.

147. Jakob 2003, p. 471-472.

148. Ass. 2001.D-2218: 5'-6', 11'-12', 17'-18', 23', 28'; Frahm 2002, p. 75.

149. Frahm 2002, p. 80. Similarly Postgate 2013, p. 22.

150. *KAJ* 310: 47; *KAV* 100: 20; **qaltu saḥputu*; pl. *qašātu saḥpātu*.

151. *KAV* 100: 19.

152. *CAD* M/I, 412b.

153. Ass. 2001.D-2279: 1.11; Frahm 2002, p. 82 n. 66.

154. Postgate 2004, p. 457b.

The *tilpānu*-weapon is a type of bow, as evidenced by the lexical lists where it is equated with *qaštu*.¹⁵⁵ However, the fact that they appear together in a document from Assur indicates that they present two different types of bows.¹⁵⁶

2.5.2 Arrows

Evidently, the use of a bow made it possible to fire arrows (*lištaḥū*)¹⁵⁷ at the enemy, in order to provoke the break up their formation and weaken them early in the combat.

An arrow was composed of a metal tip (*qaqqudu* = SAG.DU) and a wooden/reed shaft (determinative GIŠ for wooden objects in some attestations).¹⁵⁸ The arrow-tips were made of bronze,¹⁵⁹ but also of iron.¹⁶⁰

The weight of arrow-tips has been attested in one text to date. According to a receipt from Assur, an arrow-tip weighed one and a half shekels (12.45 g); i.e. 513 arrow-tips of an unspecified metal weighed twelve and two thirds minas and six shekels (6.38 kg).¹⁶¹ It is not clear whether this was a standardised weight, but these arrow tips were considerably heavier than the arrow tips weighing 1.9 g attested in the Ebla documentation, which, according to Waetzoldt, was the usual weight for arrow tips in Mesopotamia.¹⁶²

It seems that the arrow length was variable. At least, we find long arrows (*namaddu arku*, “long measure”), which implies that there were short arrows (**namaddu kuru'u*).¹⁶³ In the same document, and as in the case of the bows (see above), we find a distinction between the arrows “of the king’s hand” (*ša qāt šarri*) and *ilku*-arrows.¹⁶⁴

155. HĀR-gud VII A 61-62 (*MSL* 6, 109) and *Malku* = *šarru* III 17 (Hrūša 2010, p. 74); see already Durand 1983, p. 336-340; Groneberg 1987, p. 115-124; *CAD* T 414, “bow(?)”; Postgate 2004, p. 457, “composite bow”; see previously the bibliography cited by Groneberg 1987, p. 116 n. 8; *contra* Sasson 1969, p. 25, “throwstick”; Salonen 1965, p. 66, 148, “Wurfholz” and *AHW*. 1359, “ein Wurfholz”.

156. Ass. 2001.D-2279; Frahm 2002, p. 82.

157. Logographically written KAK.ÚTAG.GA^{MES}, *KAJ* 310: 52.50; *KAV* 195+203: 31; *BATSH* 4, 16: 5.7.18; ^{GIS}KAK.TAG.GA, *MVAG* 41/3, 16: 37; but also syllabically LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu*, *MARV* 1, 10: 1; ^{GIS}LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu*, *A* 303: 10 (quoted by Freydank 1991, p. 167); LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu*^{MES}, *MARV* 1, 10: 11.15; LIŠ-*ta-ḥu*^{MES}, *MARV* 10, 3: 11.12; LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥi*, *MARV* 63: 1; *MARV* 1, 72: 1; LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥi*^{MES}, *MARV* 9, 85: 3; LIŠ-*ta-ḥi*^{MES}, *MARV* 5, 47: 2; and once *ši-il-ta-ḥu*, *Billa* 46: 1, which indicates that LIŠ- is only a graphic metathesis; Reiner 1982, p. 93. LIŠ-*ta-ḥi* might be attested as a personal name in *A* 1775: 5, cited in Donbaz 1998, p. 184. No other term that the dictionaries translate as arrow such as *kaksū*, *mulmullu*, *šukūdu* or *uššu* has been found so far in the Middle Assyrian archival documentation. *Šiltaḥu*, *mulmullu*, *ūšū* or *uššu*, *kaksū*, *elamkū*, *su-ru-du*, *šukūdu* are listed as synonyms in *Malku* = *šarru* iii 12-16 (Hrūša 2010, p. 74).

158. Postgate 2004, p. 457a. A third part, the feathered tail, is not mentioned in our documentation; *cf.* Mayer 2003, p. 371.

159. 20 LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu* UD.KA.BAR^{MES}, *MARV* 1, 10: 1; and the archaeological fund, e.g. Eickhoff 1985, T 108.

160. ⁵⁾AN.BAR ṛša⁷ EN-li KAK.ÚTA[G.G]A^{MES} ⁶⁾a-na e-pa-še i-di-na-ni ⁷⁾20 KAK.ÚTAG.GA^{MES} ⁸⁾i+na ŠĀ-bi-šu e-ta-pa-ās, “The iron, which my lord gave to me to produce arrow(-tip)s – I have done twenty arrow(-tip)s from it”, *BATSH* 4, 16: 5-8 (letter of Šulmu to Aššur-iddin; reign of Tukulti-Ninurta I).

161. ¹⁵me 13 SAG.DU^{MES} ²⁾LIŠ-*ta-ḥi*^{MES} šā 1 ½ GÍN.TA.ĀM ³⁾ša il-ki ⁴⁾12 2/3 ma-na 6 GÍN KLLĀ, *MARV* 5, 47: 1-4.

162. Waetzoldt 1990, p. 6; but compare heads of arrow of 6 shekels (48-50 g) in Mari (Sasson 1969, p. 26); Mayer 2003, p. 372 n. 7 mentions arrow-tips from Mari weighing ¼ (2 g) to 6 shekels (50 g); Arkhipov 2012, p. 124 reports weights in a range from 45 grains (2.25 g) to five shekels (41.5 g).

163. ¹⁾20 LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu* UD.KA.BAR^{MES} na-mad-du ²⁾ar-ku ša ŠU LUGAL, “20 bronze arrows, long measurement, of the king’s hand” *MARV* 1, 10: 1-2; also 8 LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu*^{MES} na-mad-du ṛar-ku⁷ line 11 and PAB 28 LIŠ-*ta-a-ḥu*^{MES} na-mad-du ar-ku ša ŠU LUGAL ša ^{GIS}GIGIR ša GĪR LUGAL, “altogether: 28 arrows, long measure, of the king’s hand, of the chariot of the foot of the king”, lines 15-16. Various types of arrows are also attested in Old Babylonian: Mayer 2003, p. 370.

164. *MARV* 1, 10: 1-2, 15-16; see also 2 *lim* LIŠ-*ta-ḥu* il-ku, *MARV* 1, 72: 1.

Arrows appear in our documentation in large numbers, i.e. several thousand:

4 LIM⁷/ME 70⁷ x x SAG.DU LIŠ-*ta-ḫi*, “four thousand ... arrow-tips”, *MARV* 1, 63: 1 (Ep. Ibri-šarri, Tiglath-pileser I);

2 LIM LIŠ-*ta-ḫi il-ki*, “two thousand *ilku*-arrows”, *MARV* 1, 72: 1.

They are often attested with bows in the same document:

x LIŠ-*ta-ḫi*^{MEŠ}, *MARV* 9, 85: 3 (damaged document; line 1: 20 PAN^{MEŠ});

LIŠ-*ta-ḫu*, *MARV* 10, 3: 11.12 (along with bows; line 12: 55 ^{GIŠ}PAN^{MEŠ});

or with other weapons:

^{GIŠ}LIŠ-*ta-a-ḫu*, A 303: 10¹⁶⁵ along with *nar'amtu* and *pariangu* (see above);

or as a present sent to foreign kings. Arrows (*lištāḫū*), Ass.2001.D-2279¹⁶⁶ are sent as a present to the Šubrian king, along with bows (*tilpānu* and **qaltu*).

Arrows appear in inventories:

50 KAK.Ú.TAG.GA^{MEŠ}, *KAJ* 310: 52;

50 SAG.DU KAK.Ú.TAG.GA, *KAJ* 310: 59¹⁶⁷

^{GIŠ}*tup-né-na ša* KAK.Ú!.TAG.GA^{MEŠ}, *KAV* 195 + 203: 31;¹⁶⁸

1 ši-*il-ta-ḫu*, *Billa* 46: 1.¹⁶⁹

According to Akkermans and Wiggermann, 100 arrow-tips are attested in an (unpublished) document from Tell Sabi Abyad.¹⁷⁰

The twingod, ⁴MAŠ.TAB.BA, receives two arrows along with two sheep as an offering during the royal coronation.¹⁷¹

Bows and arrows were used by the units of archers (**ša qalte* (?) = (LÚ.)PAN) of the Assyrian army. As Postgate has shown, their presence and their number were greater than had previously been assumed.¹⁷² These archers were garrisoned in the capital Assur,¹⁷³ Kār-Tukulti-Ninurta,¹⁷⁴ but also at the outposts of the kingdom, such as Harbe¹⁷⁵ and Tell Sabi Abyad.¹⁷⁶

The *ḫutigu* was a part of the bowmen's weaponry, but, it is attested only once (*KAJ* 310: 46), and its meaning cannot be obtained from this single attestation.

165. Freydank 1991, p. 167.

166. Frahm 2002, p. 82.

167. Postgate 1988, no. 50.

168. Freydank, Saporetti 1989, p. 31, 70.

169. Finkelstein 1953, p. 161.

170. Akkermans, Wiggermann 1999, p. 63.

171. 2 ^{GIŠ}KAK.TAG.GA, MVAG 41/3, 16: 38 (royal ritual).

172. Postgate 2008, p. 83-92.

173. Most of the personnel lists in Llop 2009 are lists of archers and their families. See also *MARV* 8, 14 r. 13 (restored).

174. *MARV* 2, 6 I 1.10.16.20.32.35.41.67 II 5.6.14.16.19.32.33.38.47.54.60 III 17.18.21 III 24, 26, 31, 48 IV 2; 7; 11: 34⁷; 36⁷; IV 50⁷; V 33⁷; 35⁷; 36⁷; 40⁷; 73⁷; 78⁷; 84⁷; VI 3, 12, 18; *MARV* 2, 17: 85; *MARV* 4, 28: 5⁷-7⁷; Rs. 8; 10⁷; 11⁷; 15⁷; 21⁷; *MARV* 4, 29: 1⁷ (uncertain); *MARV* 4, 30: 15⁷ (uncertain); *MARV* 4, 89 I 7; 16; 19; 20; II 7; 8; II 20; 28; 35; II 46; 51; *MARV* 4, 119: 6 (see Freydank 2012, p. 229); *MARV* 4, 155: 92 (restored).

175. Jakob 2009, no. 69: 1, r. 2⁷; 5⁷; 6⁷; no. 70: 1, 8, 10, 16, 21, 25, 27, 29, 34, 39, 46, 50, 52, 54 (Elamites, *elamiāyū*, line 51); no. 71: [1], 8; no. 72: 2; no. 73: 2.

176. Wiggermann, personal communication.

2.5.3 Quivers

Unlike to bows, quivers are rarely attested in the Middle Assyrian documentation. A quiver (*išpatu*, Assyrian *išputu*) is attested in a damaged document along with other (possibly metal) objects delivered in the house of Saggiu.¹⁷⁷ A second one is a quiver for the front of a chariot in a storeroom-inventory from Assur.¹⁷⁸

2.6 Missiles (projectiles), slings

The presence of units of slingers is documented e.g. in Mari's army¹⁷⁹ and later in the Neo-Assyrian army.¹⁸⁰ Postgate has recently proposed interpreting the grapheme ša *uš-pi* (a reading ša *ús-pi* is also possible) as slinger in the Middle Assyrian lists of personnel.¹⁸¹ So far only persons have been qualified slingers; the weapon as such is not mentioned.

The ultimate weapon during the Late Bronze Age was the war chariot. But, for reasons of space, we will leave it for a future communication.

The present study discusses, the defensive and offensive weapons used by the Middle Assyrian warrior. The information proceeds mainly from the archival documentation. The defensive weapons were the helmet (*qurpisu*) or hat (*kubšu*), armour (**sariu*) and the shield (*arittu*). The offensive weapons can be divided into those used for close combat and weapons for distance combat. The close combat weapons are the stick (*haṭtu*), the whip (*maḥittu*), possibly the mace (*kakku*), the dagger or sword (*patru*), various types of axes (*ḥaššinnu*, *pāšu*, **pāltu* and *ulmu*) and the lance. Weapons for long range combat were the spear, the bow and arrows and the sling, used to throw projectiles.

As we have seen, the weaponry of the Assyrian army in the Middle Assyrian period was not very different or superior to that of other neighbouring kingdoms (such as Mittani and Babylonia). The relative success of the Assyrian army during the Middle Assyrian period, especially during the reigns of Adad-nārārī I, Shalmaneser I and Tukulti-Ninurta I, was possibly due to its organisation and the use of astute policies. The fact that the weaponry or tactics of the Assyrian were not really superior to other contemporaries is evidenced by the appearance of the Arameans, a nation of more mobile semi-nomads, who may well overwhelmed the Assyrians by weight of

177. Postgate, Collon 1999-2001, p. 8: 1. Postgate does not exclude an identification of this Saggiu with the *masennu* bearing the same name.

178. *KAJ* 310: 52; Postgate 1988, no. 50 (reign of Shalmaneser I).

179. Sasson 1969, p. 26. For a recent treatment of the slingers in Mesopotamia see Schrakamp 2009b, p. 222-225.

180. They usually appear at the rear of archers (note that they are sons of archers in the Middle Assyrian documentation); see the reliefs of Sennacherib in Barnett, Bleibtreu, Turner 1998, pl. 324-325 (WA 124904) (Reade 2004, p. 66, fig. 70) and Reade 2004, p. 28, fig. 19 (WA 124789). From a philological point of view: *a/ušpu*, Parpola 2007, p. 10, 131.

181. A syllabical value "uš" for the sign UŠ is not attested at present in Middle Assyrian; von Soden, Röellig 1991, no. 138. We should add the following passages to those discussed by Postgate 2008, p. 87, *MARV* 5, 15 IV[?] 3; *WVDOG* 124, no. 34: 8; 37: 8'.

numbers; in any case, they routed the Assyrian armies and invaded the Assyrian core territories in the 11th century BC.

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